

GROWTH AND INCOME INEQUALITIES IN HIMACHAL PRADESH: DISTRICT-WISE ANALYSIS

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The present empirical study deals with the pace of growth and measurement of income inequalities among different districts of Himachal Pradesh state. For this purpose, we have compiled district-wise information on Gross Value Added (at current prices) at aggregated and disaggregated levels, available for the period from 2011–12 to 2017–18 from ESO, Himachal Pradesh. Rates of growth in different aggregates were computed through the usual exponential trend approach. Through such an analysis, we have identified certain districts (like Chamba, Kinnaur and Lahaul & Spiti) which have been growing at a pace slower than that of the state as a whole. For measuring the extent of income inequalities, we have made use of alternative quantitative indexes, viz. Gini, Pietra-Ricci, Atkinson, Theil, Kolm, CV and Entropy. Of these, Theil's measure happened to be most sensitive to temporal changes. Extent of harmony among the alternative measures was assessed through correlation analysis. Severe inequalities were prevalent in respect of per capita income from secondary sector. Findings from the analysis are expected to provide useful policy input for achieving balanced growth among different districts of the state.

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INTRODUCTION

During the post-liberalisation policy regime, certain pockets of the Indian economy have witnessed a rapid growth in the services sector, coupled with a moderate shifting of workforce from agriculture to services sector. As a consequence, though the economy at the aggregated level has experienced a fast rate of growth as also declining trends in poverty, yet income inequalities have been reported to have increased temporally (Chauhan *et al.*, 2016; Chancel and Piketty, 2017). Shift in employment might have contributed to increasing income inequalities, because wage rate in most of the industrial activities and services is comparatively higher than that in agriculture sector (Rama *et al.*, 2015). Researchers like Bhaumik and Chakrabarty, 2006 have highlighted the importance of examining inter-regional disparities. Within developed states, economic inequality has increased – within urban areas as also

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between urban and rural areas (Deaton and Dreze, 2002; Chauhan *et al.*, 2016). Within-state inequalities explain most of the overall level of inequality and its trend. Specifically, for rural India, between-district inequality has been shown to constitute a substantial proportion of total inequality (Azam and Bhat, 2016). Chakravarty, 2001 and Chakravarty, 2006 have contributed towards decomposition of income inequality measure into constituent components. In the context of Himachal Pradesh state, Sethi and Thakur, 2020 have examined inter-district disparities with respect to social sector activities. However, the latest information on the pattern of growth and income inequalities among the districts of the hilly state of Himachal Pradesh state seems to be lacking. Therefore, the present empirical study was taken up. Findings from the study are expected to enable us to draw useful policy implications for achieving balanced growth among different districts of the state.

DATA AND ANALYTICS

For the present analysis, we have compiled district-wise data on Gross Value Added (at current prices) at aggregated and disaggregated levels (into 21 components) for each of the 12 districts [*viz.*, Bilaspur (BLSP), Chamba (CHMB), Hamirpur (HMRP), Kullu (KLLU), Kangra (KNGR), Kinnaur (KNUR), Lahaul & Spiti (LSPT), Mandi (MNDI), Shimla (SHML), Solan (SOLN) Sirmaur (SRMR), and Una (UNNA)] available for 7-year period from 2011–12 to 2017–18. Data compilation was made from Economic & Statistical Office, Himachal Pradesh. Information was also obtained on population of the districts during different years. The so-compiled data on nominal GVA were taken as *proxy* for *apparent income* of the districts at different points in time.

Suitable clubbing of the components was made so as to obtain income for *three* major sectors (*viz.* Primary, Secondary and Tertiary) at different points in time for each of the districts. From these computations, income *per capita* was also obtained for the purpose of further analysis.

As regards methodology, rate of growth in a time series $\{Y_t\}$ on a given aggregate was computed through the usual exponential approach as

$$GR (\%) = (\hat{\beta}_1 - 1) \times 100 \quad \dots(2.1)$$

where $\hat{\beta}_1$ represents the OLS estimator of β_1 obtained through the log-linearised version of

$$Y_t = \beta_0 \beta_1^t e^{u_t} \quad \dots(2.2)$$

Through the analysis, we have tried to identify the districts which have been growing at a pace slower than that of the state as a whole.

Cross-sectional and temporal differences in per capita income were examined through *two-way analysis of variance*. Further, for measuring income inequalities, we have made use of a number of alternative indexes, such as Gini 1912, 1921; Pietra 1915 and Ricci 1916; Atkinson 1970; Theil 1967; Kolm 1976; CV measure and Generalised Entropy measure, as per the following formulation:

$$\text{Gini Index: } G = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n |x_i - x_j|}{2n^2 \bar{x}} \quad \dots (2.3)$$

$$\text{Pietra-Ricci Index: } P = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |x_i - \bar{x}|}{2n\bar{x}} \quad \dots (2.4)$$

$$\text{Atkinson Index: } A = 1 - \frac{\prod_{i=1}^n \{x_i^{(1/n)}\}}{\bar{x}} \quad \dots (2.5)$$

$$\text{Theil-T Index: } T = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i}{\bar{x}} \ln \left(\frac{x_i}{\bar{x}} \right) \quad \dots (2.6)$$

$$\text{Kolm's Index: } K = \bar{x} \ln \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \exp \left(\frac{\bar{x} - x_i}{\bar{x}} \right) \right] \quad \dots (2.7)$$

$$\text{CV Measure: } C = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2}}{\bar{x}} \quad \dots (2.8)$$

$$\text{Entropy Measure: } E = \frac{1}{\alpha(1-\alpha)} \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{x_i}{\bar{x}} \right)^\alpha - 1 \right]; \alpha \neq 0, 1 \quad \dots (2.9)$$

In these indexes, x_i is the observed income for the i -th district, n ($=12$) is the number of districts and \bar{x} is the mean income of all the districts. Characteristic properties of some such indexes have been outlined in Coulter, 2018, and Rita and Sébastien, 2019. It may be mentioned that for computing Kolm's index, we first arranged the districts in an ascending order of magnitude w.r.t. their level of income on per capita basis. It may further be mentioned that the generalised entropy measure has several income inequality metrics as special cases. For example, $1 - \exp(E)$ is Atkinson index, $E(0)$ is the mean log deviation, $E(1)$ is the Theil index, and $E(2)$ is half the squared coefficient of variation.

Each of the indexes was determined at all the available points in time. Extent of harmony among the indexes was assessed through correlation analysis. And relative superiority of the indexes was gauged through their temporal sensitivity.

MAIN FINDINGS

Analytical computations from the analysis have been discussed in brief under *three* broadheads. The first head is devoted to the analysis of the rates of growth in Aggregated/Disaggregated Domestic Product (at Current Prices) in Various Districts of Himachal Pradesh. Temporal fluctuations in per capita income among the districts have been dealt with under the second head. And, inequalities among the districts have been discussed under the third head.

Rates of Growth Analysis

Average annual rates of growth in nominal DDP of Himachal Pradesh state computed at Aggregated/Disaggregated levels are presented in Table 1 and Figure 1. Barring a few exceptions (like primary sector in Bilaspur, Chamba, Kinnaur, Lahaul & Spiti and Shimla), the rates of growth were statistically highly significant ($p < 0.01$). Coefficients of Variation (CV) in the rates of growth experienced by the districts were computed to be 77.1 per cent for primary sector, 37.4 per cent for secondary sector, 5.0 per cent for tertiary sector, 19.6 for aggregated GDDP and 20.9 per cent for per capita income. Thus, as is also evident from Figure 1, inter-district variations in the rates of growth were very wide in respect of primary sector, but were quite low in respect of tertiary sector.

For the state as a whole, rates of growth in primary, secondary and tertiary sectors were computed to be 7.0 per cent, 10.3 per cent and 12.2 per cent per annum (with overall

Table 1
Exponential Rates of Growth in Aggregated/Disaggregated GDDP of Himachal Pradesh State (2011–12 to 2017–18)

<i>District</i>	<i>Aggregate</i>	<i>Exponential rate of growth</i>	<i>t-Value</i>	<i>p-Value</i>
Bilaspur	Primary	-1.61	0.766	0.4781
	Secondary	13.15	7.288	0.0008
	Tertiary	11.85	20.878	<0.0001
	GDDP	9.39	12.607	0.0001
	PCI	8.75	11.041	0.0001
Chamba	Primary	2.22	0.856	0.4313
	Secondary	3.89	7.255	0.0008
	Tertiary	11.96	24.703	<0.0001
	GDDP	6.55	8.648	0.0003
	PCI	5.93	7.273	0.0008
Hamirpur	Primary	15.05	3.624	0.0152
	Secondary	6.78	8.494	0.0004
	Tertiary	12.51	27.357	<0.0001
	GDDP	11.94	15.513	<0.0001
	PCI	11.28	13.923	<0.0001
Kangra	Primary	7.37	5.861	0.0021
	Secondary	7.11	13.928	<0.0001
	Tertiary	12.49	24.758	<0.0001
	GDDP	10.46	20.814	<0.0001
	PCI	9.82	17.701	<0.0001
Kinnaur	Primary	4.33	0.932	0.3942
	Secondary	5.63	7.859	0.0005
	Tertiary	10.94	20.676	<0.0001
	GDDP	7.25	4.672	0.0055
	PCI	6.63	4.200	0.0085

Table 1 contd....

<i>District</i>	<i>Aggregate</i>	<i>Exponential rate of growth</i>	<i>t-Value</i>	<i>p-Value</i>
Kullu	Primary	4.92	1.388	0.2237
	Secondary	6.08	7.795	0.0006
	Tertiary	11.24	29.778	<0.0001
	GDDP	8.24	8.002	0.0005
	PCI	7.60	7.159	0.0008
Lahaul & Spiti	Primary	0.38	0.166	0.8749
	Secondary	9.13	6.247	0.0015
	Tertiary	11.24	19.087	<0.0001
	GDDP	7.64	6.716	0.0011
	PCI	7.01	6.207	0.0016
Mandi	Primary	9.11	5.625	0.0025
	Secondary	6.50	7.078	0.0009
	Tertiary	12.08	24.325	<0.0001
	GDDP	10.32	19.468	<0.0001
	PCI	9.68	16.305	<0.0001
Shimla	Primary	8.84	2.451	0.0579
	Secondary	7.35	7.301	0.0008
	Tertiary	12.16	41.328	<0.0001
	GDDP	10.06	9.487	0.0002
	PCI	9.42	8.501	0.0004
Sirmaur	Primary	3.77	1.302	0.2498
	Secondary	13.56	12.984	<0.0001
	Tertiary	12.90	61.574	<0.0001
	GDDP	11.65	23.730	<0.0001
	PCI	11.00	20.679	<0.0001
Solan	Primary	11.13	7.470	0.0007
	Secondary	12.10	48.175	<0.0001
	Tertiary	12.38	23.926	<0.0001
	GDDP	12.09	46.047	<0.0001
	PCI	11.44	40.328	<0.0001
Una	Primary	7.72	4.347	0.0074
	Secondary	10.70	16.818	<0.0001
	Tertiary	12.34	15.811	<0.0001
	GDDP	11.12	52.017	<0.0001
	PCI	10.47	38.502	<0.0001
Entire State	Primary	7.02	6.461	0.0013
	Secondary	10.31	37.981	<0.0001
	Tertiary	12.20	28.684	<0.0001
	GDDP	10.56	27.703	<0.0001
	PCI	9.91	22.191	<0.0001

Figure 1
Relative Comparison of Exponential Rates of Growth (%) in Different Aggregates of
GDDP of Himachal Pradesh State

GSDP having grown at a rate of 10.6%). On the whole, the rate of growth in tertiary sector was tested to be highly significantly faster than that in primary sector ($p = 0.0007$), but was just significantly larger than that in secondary sector ($p = 0.0430$). The difference between rates of growth in primary and secondary sectors could not be detected to be significant ($p = 0.2047$).

Subsequently, an attempt was made to assign ranks to the districts on the basis of their performance on rates of growth registered in different aggregates (Table 2). As is evident from the table, the districts like Hamirpur, Solan and Sirmaur have performed significantly better than the state as a whole whereas, on the other extreme, the districts like Chamba, Kinnaur and Lahaul & Spiti were the poor-performing districts *vis-à-vis* the state as a whole. The findings thus call for the need to pay due attention to the slow-growing districts so as to enhance parity among districts of the state.

Comparative Performance of the Districts on Per Capita Income

Relative values of nominal per capita income (at both aggregated and at disaggregated levels) of different districts and temporal fluctuations therein have been depicted in Figure 2.

As is evident from the figure, relative standing of the districts is peculiar to the economic activity. For instance, tribal districts like Kinnaur and Lahaul & Spiti were the leaders in respect of per capita income from primary sector, possible because of (a) low population density, and cultivation of high-value horticultural crops (like apples, saffron, etc.). Solan district

Table 2
Ranking of Districts (in an Ascending Order of Magnitude) on the basis of Exponential Growth Rate (EGR in %) in Different Aggregates

District	EGR of PRMR sector	District	EGR of SCDR sector	District	EGR of TRTR sector	District	EGR of AGG GDDP	District	EGR of PCIN
Bilaspur	-1.61	Chamba	3.89	Kinnaur	10.94	Chamba	6.55	Chamba	5.93
Lahaul & Spiti	0.38	Kinnaur	5.63	Kullu	11.24	Kinnaur	7.25	Kinnaur	6.63
Chamba	2.22	Kullu	6.08	Lahaul & Spiti	11.24	Lahaul & Spiti	7.64	Lahaul & Spiti	7.01
Sirmaur	3.77	Mandi	6.50	Bilaspur	11.85	Kullu	8.24	Kullu	7.60
Kinnaur	4.33	Hamirpur	6.78	Chamba	11.96	Bilaspur	9.39	Bilaspur	8.75
Kullu	4.92	Kangra	7.11	Mandi	12.08	Shimla	10.06	Shimla	9.42
Entire State	7.02	Shimla	7.35	Shimla	12.16	Mandi	10.32	Mandi	9.68
Kangra	7.37	Lahaul & Spiti	9.13	Entire State	12.20	Kangra	10.46	Kangra	9.82
Una	7.72	Entire State	10.31	Una	12.34	Entire State	10.56	Entire State	9.91
Shimla	8.84	Una	10.70	Solan	12.38	Una	11.12	Una	10.47
Mandi	9.11	Solan	12.10	Kangra	12.49	Sirmaur	11.65	Sirmaur	11.00
Solan	11.13	Bilaspur	13.15	Hamirpur	12.51	Hamirpur	11.94	Hamirpur	11.28
Hamirpur	15.05	Sirmaur	13.56	Sirmaur	12.90	Solan	12.09	Solan	11.44

● : Pace of Growth in the Entire State; ●, Districts Growing at a Pace Slower than the Entire State; ●, Districts Growing at a Pace Faster than the Entire State.

Figure 2
Inter district Differentials in per Capita Income at Different Points in Time
(at Aggregated and Disaggregated Levels)

happened to be leader in respect of per capita income from secondary sector, most likely because of a large number of pharmaceutical and other manufacturing units located in the township of *Baddi* of the district. The tribal districts of Lahaul & Spiti and Kinnaur again happened to be the leaders on tertiary sector activities, owing primarily to a fairly large chunk of their population occupying key positions in services sector because of reservation policy for STs.

In order to draw concrete conclusions from the cross-sectional-*cum*-temporal variations in per capita income from different economic activities, we have sought the help of *two-way ANOVA* technique. As per the analytical findings (Table 3), significant inter-district as well as inter-temporal variations (though at varying probability levels) were detected in respect of all the sectors.

Inter-District Inequalities with Respect to Aggregated/ Disaggregated per Capita Income

At each of the seven points in time, computations of different indexes of inequality among 12 districts of Himachal Pradesh state were computed with respect to per capita income (at

Table 3
Computed Values of F-Statistic for Inter-District and Inter-Temporal Comparisons w.r.t. Per Capita Income

<i>Sector</i>	<i>Inter-district variations</i>		<i>Inter-temporal variations</i>	
	<i>F-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>F-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>
Primary	51.093***	<0.0001	3.013*	0.0115
Secondary	123.458***	<0.0001	3.936**	0.0020
Tertiary	157.100***	<0.0001	183.200***	<0001
Overall Economy	117.590***	<0.0001	17.170***	<0001

***Significant at 0.1% level; **Significant at 1% level; *Significant at 5% level

aggregated/disaggregated levels; Table 4). It may be mentioned that Kolm's index failed to provide us with finite values and was, therefore, disregarded. Matrices of intercorrelation coefficients among the remaining six indexes have been presented in Table 5.

Table 4
Computations on Different Indexes of Inter-District Inequalities w.r.t. PCI

<i>Sector</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i>Index</i>					
		<i>G</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>E</i>
Primary	2012	0.309	0.224	0.084	0.160	0.556	0.173
	2013	0.331	0.227	0.093	0.186	0.639	0.190
	2014	0.357	0.247	0.110	0.219	0.690	0.227
	2015	0.352	0.252	0.108	0.213	0.684	0.221
	2016	0.312	0.214	0.088	0.168	0.587	0.180
	2017	0.392	0.270	0.134	0.275	0.817	0.277
	2018	0.338	0.246	0.099	0.189	0.610	0.204
	CV	8.435	8.049	16.506	19.385	13.232	17.015
	Secondary	2012	0.557	0.414	0.272	0.632	1.435
2013		0.554	0.413	0.267	0.621	1.419	0.575
2014		0.563	0.425	0.274	0.640	1.446	0.591
2015		0.575	0.437	0.284	0.664	1.471	0.616
2016		0.574	0.436	0.284	0.667	1.485	0.615
2017		0.594	0.455	0.302	0.716	1.551	0.659
2018		0.602	0.464	0.311	0.745	1.596	0.681
CV		3.149	4.528	5.773	6.826	4.361	6.318
Tertiary		2012	0.352	0.265	0.116	0.217	0.655
	2013	0.349	0.262	0.115	0.215	0.651	0.236
	2014	0.354	0.266	0.117	0.218	0.654	0.241
	2015	0.355	0.266	0.118	0.221	0.659	0.244
	2016	0.356	0.267	0.119	0.222	0.662	0.246
	2017	0.355	0.265	0.118	0.22	0.657	0.244
	2018	0.355	0.267	0.118	0.221	0.660	0.243
	CV	0.649	0.645	1.347	1.206	0.599	1.390

Table 4 contd....

Sector	Year	Index					
		G	R	A	T	C	E
Overall	2012	0.400	0.292	0.138	0.273	0.780	0.287
	2013	0.394	0.29	0.134	0.264	0.764	0.278
	2014	0.404	0.299	0.141	0.278	0.785	0.293
	2015	0.404	0.298	0.142	0.279	0.786	0.295
	2016	0.400	0.298	0.140	0.277	0.785	0.291
	2017	0.421	0.314	0.154	0.306	0.830	0.322
	2018	0.418	0.310	0.153	0.305	0.841	0.318
	CV	2.475	2.919	5.224	5.660	3.561	5.439

Table 5
Matrices of Intercorrelation Coefficients among the Indexes of Inequality

Sector	Index	Index [#]					
		G	R	A	T	C	E
Primary	G	1.000	0.949	0.992	0.991	0.977	0.991
	P	0.949	1.000	0.935	0.917	0.873	0.937
	A	0.992	0.935	1.000	0.997	0.979	1.000
	T	0.991	0.917	0.997	1.000	0.992	0.996
	C	0.977	0.873	0.979	0.992	1.000	0.976
	E	0.991	0.937	1.000	0.996	0.976	1.000
Secondary	G	1.000	0.997	0.996	0.994	0.988	0.995
	P	0.997	1.000	0.987	0.985	0.978	0.985
	A	0.996	0.987	1.000	0.999	0.996	1.000
	T	0.994	0.985	0.999	1.000	0.998	0.999
	C	0.988	0.978	0.996	0.998	1.000	0.995
	E	0.995	0.985	1.000	0.999	0.995	1.000
Tertiary	G	1.000	0.912	0.973	0.951	0.878	0.972
	P	0.912	1.000	0.853	0.860	0.852	0.831
	A	0.973	0.853	1.000	0.983	0.930	0.994
	T	0.951	0.860	0.983	1.000	0.966	0.975
	C	0.878	0.852	0.930	0.966	1.000	0.916
	E	0.972	0.831	0.994	0.975	0.916	1.000
Overall	G	1.000	0.979	0.995	0.992	0.971	0.996
	P	0.979	1.000	0.985	0.981	0.951	0.987
	A	0.995	0.985	1.000	0.998	0.983	0.999
	T	0.992	0.981	0.998	1.000	0.990	0.998
	C	0.971	0.951	0.983	0.990	1.000	0.978
	E	0.996	0.987	0.999	0.998	0.978	1.000

[#]G: Gini; P: Pietra-Ricci; A: Atkinson; T: Theil; C: CV Measure; E: Entropy

A glance at Table 4 reveals that in respect of per capita income from, say, primary sector, Theil's measure (T) was associated with the highest value (= 19.4%) of the coefficient of variation. Except for per capita income from tertiary sector, the measure was associated with the highest value of CV in respect of the other two aggregates as well. Thus, from the angle of *sensitivity to temporal changes*, Theil's measure could be accepted, in general, to be the most appropriate index of income inequalities among the districts of Himachal Pradesh state. A perusal of Table 5 indicates that except for Pietra-Ricci index (P), Theil's index (T) was very strongly associated ($r \approx 0.99$, in general) with the rest of the indexes. We may thus say that Theil's measure had a strong tendency to move hand-in-hand with the other indexes, thus providing a further justification to gauge the extent of inequalities on the basis of just one of the indexes, *viz.*, T.

Diagrammatical presentation of extent of inter-district inequalities (as gauged from Theil's measure T) with respect to per capita income from different economic activities (Figure 3) brings out certain revelations, such as (a) Inequalities were exceptionally high with respect to per capita income from secondary sector and that these have been rising over a period of time; (b) Income inequalities in respect of primary sector have been experiencing wide temporal fluctuations; (c) Income inequalities in respect of tertiary sector have remained, more or

Figure 3
Temporal Changes in Theil's Measure (T) of Income Inequalities

less, static at a fairly low level; and (d) Inequalities in respect of overall per capita income have shown a slight tendency to rise over a period of time, resulting primarily from the extent of inequalities in secondary sector. The findings thus call for a need to adopt suitable measures to curb the extent of inter-district inequalities w.r.t. income from secondary sector.

CONCLUDING REMARKS AND POLICY IMPLICATION

Analytical findings from the analysis have thus revealed that districts like Chamba, Kinnaur and Lahaul & Spiti of Himachal Pradesh have performed rather poorly in comparison to the state as a whole. There is thus a need for the state government to pay due attention to the slow-growing districts so as to enhance parity among districts of the state. Further, in the light of high extent and temporally rising inequalities in respect of per capita income from secondary sector, there is a dire need to identify different pockets having comparative advantage and adopt suitable corrective measures which could ensure a horizontal spread of manufacturing activities among different districts of the state.

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